

COMPARATIVE EVALUATION OF POSITIVE PSYCHOLOGY INTERVENTION PRACTICES AMONG FILIPINO CLINICAL PSYCHOLOGY PRACTITIONERS

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Comparative Evaluation of Positive Psychology Intervention Practices Among Filipino Clinical Psychology Practitioners

Hannah Mae B. Gabuyo*, Pricila B. Marzan

For affiliations and correspondence, see the last page.

Abstract

This study investigates the implementation of Positive Psychology Interventions (PPIs) within the clinical context among clinical psychologists in the Philippines. The previous research has examined the use of PPIs with diverse populations, such as survivors of natural disasters, victims of domestic violence, overseas Filipino workers, and students, linking PPIs to their overall well-being and academic achievements. However, there are still limitations in the context of the clinical setting that need further investigation, such as the effectiveness of interventions for mental illnesses and similar conditions. Thus, this study focuses on the concept and utilization of PPIs, investigating their perceived effectiveness within the clinical psychology profession. This study employed a phenomenological approach with open-ended questions during social media interviews to gather detailed data. However, social media interviews may not fully capture the entirety of the experience. The selection of participants was carried out using a combination of purposive sampling and snowball techniques. Participants were chosen based on specific criteria: 5 years of clinical experience, a background in positive psychology interventions, and a demonstrated utilization of these interventions in their clinical sessions. The study revealed several main themes that shed light on the participants' unique observations and experiences within each domain. These themes include: 1. Integrated practice, where PPIs are seamlessly combined with traditional methods; 2. Adapted method, which explores how PPIs are tailored for use in clinical settings; 3. Applied intervention, highlighting the practical application of PPIs; 4. Personal growth, illustrating the significant contributions of PPIs to both clients and practitioners; 5. Gratitude, reflecting statements of effectiveness; 6. Holistic healing, emphasizing the advantages of integrated practices; and 7. Limitations, acknowledging constraints of PPIs' utilization. Further research is recommended to address these limitations and to expand and validate experiences within the clinical realm, contributing to the growing body of knowledge and understanding of the efficacy and applicability of PPIs in clinical psychology practice.

Keywords: *positive psychology interventions, psychology practitioners, positive psychology intervention practices, phenomenological approach*

Introduction

Martin Seligman once described positive psychology as "the scientific study of the strengths that enable individuals and communities to thrive" (Seligman, 2005). The emergence of positive psychology can be traced back to the heightened demand for mental health therapy during World War II, when the field of psychology primarily focused on the disease model. At that time, psychologists dedicated their research efforts to understanding mental illnesses and finding ways to treat them. Unfortunately, this singular focus often neglected the fundamental goals of psychology: the betterment and nurturing of individuals (Duckworth, Steen, & Seligman, 2005; Csikszentmihalyi & Seligman, 2014).

Martin Seligman, renowned for his work on learned helplessness, experienced a transformative realization that emphasized cultivating the positive aspects of human conditions (Ackerman, 2020). This marked the beginning of positive psychology's prominence when Seligman chose it as the theme for his presidency at the American Psychological Association. Positive psychology aimed to bridge the gap between the two primary concerns of pathology by directing attention to positive emotions, positive characteristics (Keyes, Fredrickson, & Park, 2012), positive institutions, positive relationships, and positive meaning (Kun, Balogh, & Krasz, 2016) — all of which contribute to human flourishing (Seligman, Steen, Park, & Peterson, 2005).

In the past decades, positive psychology has developed evidence-based interventions dedicated to enhancing individual and societal well-being, without neglecting human suffering and mental disorders. These interventions primarily focus on improving human strengths rather than weaknesses (Csikszentmihalyi & Seligman, 2014). Positive Psychology Interventions (PPIs) encompass a range of tools and strategies that have undergone rigorous study to promote happiness and well-being. They emphasize positive cognitions, positive emotions, and positive behaviors (Leontopoulou, 2015). The seven categories of PPIs include savoring, gratitude interventions, kindness boosters, Empathy PPIs, optimistic interventions, strength-building measures, and meaning-oriented PPIs (Chowdhury, 2021).

The effectiveness of PPIs has been demonstrated in various contexts. Bolier et al. (2013) cited a meta analysis by Sin and Lyubomirsky, which showed significant improvements in well-being and a reduction in depressive symptoms when PPIs were applied in clinical settings. These interventions have also found success in positive education within schools (Norrish & Green, 2013), positive organizational behavior in the workplace (Donaldson, Lee, & Donaldson, 2019), healthcare settings (Duckworth, Steen, & Seligman, 2005), and diverse cultural backgrounds (Dimitropoulou & Leontopoulou, 2017). Specific interventions, such as gratitude

interventions (Emmons & McCullough, 2003), acts of kindness (Lyubomirsky, Sheldon, & Schkade, 2005), and character strength exercises (Duckworth, Steen, & Seligman, 2005), have been tested through explicit instructions and randomized assignments to measure their effectiveness (Bolier et al., 2013). Furthermore, PPIs can also be delivered in self-help formats (Bolier et al., 2013).

Within the domains of treatment and prevention, psychologists advocate for integrating positive psychology principles to foster happiness and cultivate a fulfilling life. This approach involves savoring, utilizing signature strengths, and meaning making (Duckworth, Steen, & Seligman, 2005). For instance, PPIs have shown benefits for individuals with non-clinical diagnoses, such as those with physical health conditions like diabetes and heart diseases (Macaskill, 2016), individuals experiencing stress in an industrial setting (Chakhssi F., Kraiss, Sommers-Spijkerman, & Bohlmeijer, 2018), those dealing with burn-out syndrome (Alexiou, Kotsoni, & Stalikas, 2021), students aiming to increase self-esteem in classroom learning (Narafshan & Noori, 2018), and individuals seeking to overcome obstacles and increase motivation (Duckworth, Steen, & Seligman, 2005). PPIs have also been shown to reduce symptoms of depression, anxiety (Alexiou, Kotsoni, & Stalikas, 2021), substance abuse disorders, and even certain negative symptoms of schizophrenia, such as asociality, avolition, and anhedonia (Rashid, 2009). Additionally, PPIs have proven to be helpful in reducing pathology in individuals with severe mental illness (Geerling et al., 2020).

In recent years, positive psychology has gained significant traction in Asia, including the Philippines. The majority of research efforts in this region have focused on implementing positive psychology in school settings to help improve students academic achievements and wellbeing. For instance, a longitudinal study by Datu and Mateo (2020) cited several studies demonstrating that character strengths are correlated with higher levels of general self-efficacy, academic self-efficacy, and well-being outcomes among high school students in the Philippines. Additionally, PPIs can be applied in other situations, such as assisting survivors of natural disasters, victims of domestic violence, and overseas Filipino workers.

These investigations have made substantial contributions to the understanding of positive traits and the optimization of well-being in academic and non-academic settings. However, despite the significant contribution of Positive Psychology Interventions (PPIs) to those aforementioned settings, there is still a need to focus on the clinical context, particularly the utilization of PPIs in therapeutic practices, to enhance our understanding of their applicability and effectiveness (Datu, Bernardo, & King, 2018). Research on mental illness within the clinical context remains limited in the Philippines (Geerling et al., 2020; Datu, Bernardo, & King, 2018). Investigating Filipino psychologists' perspectives and utilization of Positive Psychology Interventions (PPIs) aims to ensure cultural appropriateness and efficacy in addressing the needs of individuals in the Philippines. By comprehensively understanding psychologists' experiences and insights, interventions can be refined to better align with the cultural context and enhance their effectiveness for the Filipino population.

Furthermore, this study aims to examine the implementation of Positive Psychology Interventions (PPIs) by practitioners during clinical sessions, with a specific focus on two aspects: (1) the practitioners' experiences in utilizing PPIs and (2) the participants' perceptions regarding the efficacy of these tools in clinical practice. These research objectives are aligned with the previous discussion on positive psychology and its applications in various settings.

Methodology

This research study involved the participation of Clinical Psychology Practitioners in the Philippines residing in Luzon and Visayas. A total of eight respondents initially took part in the study through interviews conducted via Zoom or Google Meet. Subsequently, the number of participants for the follow-up interview was reduced to five due to the following valid reasons: busy schedules and unresponsiveness, although still adequate for data saturation. The participants in this study were either private or government employees engaged in professional practices as registered psychologists. They had at least five years of clinical experience (Goldberg et al., 2016) and possessed fundamental knowledge of Positive Psychology and its interventions. In this study, a qualitative research methodology was employed to delve into the experiences, concepts, and opinions of the participants. Non-numerical data was gathered to provide a comprehensive understanding of the subject matter. Data collection took place through social media platforms, where participants shared narrative stories detailing their experiences. Subsequently, the collected data underwent transcription and analysis using Interpretative Phenomenological Analysis (IPA). IPA served as the analytical framework to explore the lived experiences of Filipino clinical psychology practitioners in their utilization of Positive Psychology Interventions. Through IPA, the researchers manually deciphered the narratives, identifying patterns, themes, and underlying meanings within the data as follows: transcribing the data from the recordings, identifying phrases and passages per participant, coding dominant themes and subthemes per participant, refining themes through constant comparison and analysis, interpreting themes in the context of participants' experiences, expert validation during initial and follow-up interviews, and writing up findings. Overall, these steps helped uncover and analyze significant insights within the data. The insights gathered from the participants not only contributed to the current study but also suggested potential avenues for future research.

To recruit participants, the researchers utilized various social media platforms such as LinkedIn, Facebook, and TherapyRoute, while one participant was recruited through a referral. Informed consent was obtained from all participants via email, providing them with detailed information about the study. The researchers employed snowball sampling, wherein participants were filtered based on specific criteria such as years of practice as a clinician, occupational employment, duration of using Positive Psychology in their sessions, and personal stories related to their knowledge of Positive Psychology and its interventions. Accepted participants were then scheduled for interviews, and arrangements for payment were made as per their preferences. Prior to the interviews, participants received a briefing,

and during the interviews, they were probed with relevant questions.

In-depth interviews were conducted to explore the participants' experiences and assessments regarding the use of Positive Psychology Interventions as part of clinical additional treatment plans or personal usage. The study also examined the effectiveness of these interventions in specific cases of mental illness and the impact of the appropriateness of the tools on their effectiveness. Due to the pandemic, data collection was carried out remotely using platforms like Zoom or other social media means to adhere to safety protocols. Follow-up interviews were conducted, and the transcriptions were carefully reviewed for further analysis.

The information presented in this study is based on the lived experiences of the participants, who were asked to narrate their stories and share their experiences as clinical psychologists in using Positive Psychology Interventions. Relevant questions were posed to the participants, focusing on their experiences and the effectiveness of these interventions in their clinical practices. The researchers also probed essential aspects, such as the efficacy of the tools and their benefits for personal and career development, to gather additional valuable data.

According to Alhazmi and Kaufmann (2022), phenomenological research differs from quantitative research in terms of questionnaire validation. Unlike quantitative research, where validation of measures and instruments is crucial for ensuring reliability and validity, phenomenological research takes a different approach. Phenomenology emphasizes the subjective nature of human experiences, aiming to capture the richness and complexity of these experiences without imposing preconceived notions or constructs. This approach has led to the conclusion of not utilizing validated questionnaires. There are several reasons for this decision. Firstly, utilizing validated questionnaires may hinder the natural capture of the rawness of human experiences or lived experiences of the participants. Secondly, phenomenology prioritizes the exploration of individual experiences, meanings, and interpretations, focusing on capturing the unique perspectives of participants rather than generalizing findings to a larger population. Thirdly, phenomenological research encourages flexibility and openness to emergent themes and insights, allowing for the exploration of new dimensions and aspects of the phenomenon under investigation. Using pre-validated questionnaires may restrict the exploration of novel or unexpected aspects that may arise during data collection. Finally, phenomenological research often relies on in-depth interviews or open-ended questions to elicit rich descriptions of experiences. These methods enable participants to express their experiences in their own words, point of view, and provide detailed, context-specific information. By using pre-validated questionnaires, researchers may inadvertently limit the depth and authenticity of the data obtained (Bevan, 2014).

Ethical considerations play a vital role in research studies. In line with this perspective, the current study strictly adheres to a set of ethical considerations, as follows: The first ethical consideration addressed by the researcher is obtaining informed consent from recruited participants. In this regard, potential participants who were selected or referred to the study were required to explicitly accept and confirm their consent, either through email or other means of communication. Participants who did not respond were subsequently excluded from the study. The informed consent letter provided a comprehensive outline of the study's purpose and the extent of participants' involvement. Before proceeding with the actual interview, participants were debriefed about the research procedures and the specific objectives the researcher aimed to investigate.

This debriefing process aimed to address any misconceptions participants may have had regarding the study. To ensure research confidentiality, the researcher took measures to protect and anonymize participants' data. Names were kept anonymous, and faces were concealed in the manuscripts and final findings. Furthermore, any recordings and exchange of communication related to the study were strictly prohibited from being disclosed to colleagues or individuals not directly involved in the research, except for the researcher's advisor. During the interview process, none of the participants withdrew their participation amidst data collection, ensuring the continuity and integrity of the study (McLeod, 2015).

Results and Discussion

The findings of this study revealed seven distinct main themes that were identified through interviews with Filipino practitioners in the Philippines. These themes provide valuable insights into the practitioners' observations and experiences, shedding light on various aspects of their practice. The seven main themes identified were as follows: integrated practice, adapted method, applied interventions, personal growth, gratitude, holistic healing, and limitations.

Each of these themes was further explored to uncover corresponding minor themes expressed by the participants. The first main theme, Integrated practice emphasized the utilization of (a). eclectic approaches as a subtheme. The practitioners discussed their implementation of various methods and techniques to provide comprehensive care. The second theme, Adapted method, highlighted (a). utilized intervention by practitioners and (b). banking on inner strengths; the practitioners' use of interventions that tapped into clients' inner strengths. Additionally, they discussed the importance of adapting methods to suit individual needs. The third theme, applied interventions, with the sub-themes of; (a). doable to mental related disorders,

(b). distressful circumstances, (c). ways in which PPI was utilized in sessions and (d). practical tools; focused on the practical aspects of using PPI (Psychotherapy and Psychological Interventions) for addressing mental health disorders and challenging circumstances. Practitioners shared specific strategies and practical tools employed during therapy sessions. The fourth theme, personal growth, delved into the significance of fostering personal development among clients. It encompassed aspects such as (a). appreciating life, (b). self-

compassion, and (c). self-improvement. The fifth theme, gratitude, explored (a). the appreciation expressed by clients for the practitioners' efforts and guidance. The sixth theme, holistic healing, emphasized the importance of cultivating a (a). proper mindset, effectively (b). managing emotions and considering (c). physical healing as integral components of the therapeutic process. Lastly, the seventh theme, limitations, encompassed factors that posed challenges to practitioners, including (a). severe mental health conditions, (b). Circumstantial, (c). environmental hindrances, and (d). client resistance.

These main themes, along with their respective minor themes, provide a comprehensive overview of the insights and experiences shared by Filipino practitioners in the Philippines.

Experiences

Integrated Practice

The participants 5, 6, and 8 (clinical practitioners) of the study acknowledged the significance of employing mixed interventions rather than exclusively focusing on a single therapeutic procedure. They recognized the value of incorporating traditional interventions, such as the Psychodynamic Approach and Cognitive-Behavioral Therapy (CBT), along with Positive Psychology Interventions (PPI) as integral components of the treatment plan. According to their perspectives, this combined approach offers substantial benefits.

Additionally, participant 6 made specific observations regarding the empirical advantages of integrating Positive Psychology with other interventions. This combination was found to tap into the clients' potential, leading to sustained benefits such as a reduction in depressive symptoms. These findings align with the research conducted by Chaves, Lopez-Gomez, Hervas, and Vazquez (2017), which demonstrated the efficacy of integrating positive interventions into patient treatment plans. By incorporating positive interventions, individuals are able to enhance treatment outcomes by leveraging their strengths and abilities to effectively address challenges while also addressing cognitive deficits.

Adapted Method

Positive Psychology Interventions have been found to be beneficial not only for clients but also for psychology practitioners themselves (participants 2, 5, 6, 8). The participants reported utilizing various interventions based on the PERMA (Positive Emotion, Engagement, Positive Relationships, Meaning, Accomplishment/Achievement) Model. These interventions included practices such as meditations and breathing exercises, gratitude interventions, strengths assessment, optimism exercises, acts of kindness, savoring positive experiences, finding meaning in life, and engaging in other activities related to positive interventions, as reported by participants 2, 6, and 8. These findings aligned with a recent meta-analysis study by Carr et al. (2020), which demonstrated that Positive Psychology Interventions, such as identifying strengths, humor, writing about positive experiences, finding meaning, solution-focused coaching, strengthening relationships, setting goals, volunteering, gratitude interventions, savoring, and more, have moderate effectiveness in promoting well-being, improving quality of life, enhancing strengths, reducing stress and depressive symptoms, and potentially shortening therapy sessions.

Furthermore, the utilization of inner strengths was emphasized as a crucial aspect of this approach. The concept of "banking on inner strengths" involves practitioners actively identifying and harnessing the innate strengths of their clients to facilitate progress in therapy. The participants' 2, 5, and 8 recognized that leveraging clients' inherent strengths provides an additional boost to the therapeutic process and plays a vital role in addressing mental health concerns. By highlighting these strengths, therapists enhance their functionality as tools or resources that clients can draw upon in future circumstances. This perspective is supported by a study conducted by Gander et al. (2013), which demonstrated the significant positive impact of utilizing signature strengths in a randomized trial that also incorporated other positive interventions. The results of that study indicated notable improvements in happiness levels and a reduction in depressive symptoms over the course of a one-month intervention period and overall wellbeing and happiness (Niemiec, 2023).

Applied Interventions

Based on the data from participants 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, and 8, applied interventions encompass the practical implementation of positive psychology principles and strategies aimed at promoting well-being for both practitioners and their clients. According to one of the allied mental health professionals, counseling practitioners integrating Positive Psychology Interventions (PPIs) into their practice stand to derive personal and professional benefits from the nuanced understanding of well-being afforded by this evolving discipline. By incorporating PPIs, counselors can broaden their repertoire of counseling techniques, fostering greater professional adaptability. Moreover, this expansion does not necessitate a fundamental reassessment of their foundational counseling assumptions or beliefs regarding the efficacy of counseling and the potential for transformative change. The potential gains elucidated by practitioners adopting a positive psychology approach extend to both personal and professional domains, thereby presenting ample opportunities for self-directed learning and individual growth (D'raven, & Pasha-Zaidi, 2014). These interventions have been found to be particularly applicable and effective in cases of mild to moderate clinical conditions. Positive Psychology Interventions (PPI) are applicable to various mental disorders, but caution is advised, with particular attention given to conditions such as depression and anxiety, which most practitioners recognize as suitable for PPI implementation (participant 4, 5 and 8). D'raven and Pasha-Zaidi (2014) stated that a positive psychology approach places emphasis on assisting clients in utilizing a variety of skills and strategies to enhance the frequency of positive emotions and experiences. This approach not only alleviates depression but also cultivates increased happiness, guiding

clients toward a state of flourishing, which supports clinical practitioners in their observation within their practice. Furthermore, PPI can also be beneficial for individuals who have experienced trauma (Wilson, 2006), including sexual, emotional, or psychological abuse (participant 4, 5, and 8). It can also be utilized effectively in distressing circumstances and life stressors, such as life adjustments, self-esteem, midlife crises, burnout, and family rejections (participants 1, 3, 4, 5, 6) (Wong, Wong, & Scott, 2006).

Additionally, regarding psychological assessment, it has been found that many clients are initially unaware of their issues and problems, requiring practitioners to assist in identifying and addressing them. For instance, individuals with depression may undergo an assessment to determine if biological symptoms or comorbid conditions contribute to their condition. Thus, leading (clinical practitioners) participants 2, 3, and 8, to decide not to inject PPIs in the beginning of the session. They observed that Positive Psychology Interventions (PPI) are most suitable for implementation in the latter part of therapy sessions. This consideration takes into account factors such as the client's physical condition and medication regimen, which can affect the effectiveness of PPIs during sessions, as noted by the participants. Participant 2 emphasized the importance of addressing the client's immediate coping needs first, particularly focusing on physical well-being. They stated, "Injection of PP in the later part of the session is because first, you are trying to help the person cope. For me, I start with the physical." Participant 3 highlighted the impact of hormonal factors on the timing of PPI implementation, stating, "Based on experience, it shouldn't be the first plan for these kinds of patients. Their hormones or chemicals in their bodies are not yet stabilized, so what we actually do is interact and team up with a psychiatrist to alleviate those symptoms. We usually wait around 2 to 3 months before introducing the PPI." Participant 8 emphasized the importance of readiness and client-centeredness in introducing PPIs, stating, "Sometimes, if my clients need to understand the problem more and can benefit from diving deeper into past trauma, need a lot of healing, and still need catharsis in that sense, then they are not ready to move forward and are not there yet. In such cases, I won't choose to introduce PPI just yet." Overall, the insights provided by these participants suggest that the timing of PPI implementation should be carefully considered, taking into account the client's individual needs and readiness for such interventions.

Finally, practitioners (participants 1, 2, 3, and 4) opt to utilize PPIs due to their non-invasive, unstructured nature, and user-friendly tools. These practical tools can be utilized in various settings, including face-to-face interactions, individual or group therapy, and even online interactions (Parks, 2015).

Personal Growth

Positive psychology interventions (PPI) can significantly contribute to personal growth by equipping individuals, including practitioners and their clients, with tools and strategies to enhance well-being and flourishing (D'raven, & Pasha-Zaidi, 2014). Beyond the benefits experienced by clients, practitioners (participants 4, 5, 6, 7, and 8) have also observed and experienced the transformative impact of PPI in their own lives. They have witnessed personal growth manifested in various ways, particularly in acknowledging and reflecting upon past experiences. Three positive effects of PPI on practitioners have been identified: (1) Self-examination: facilitated by (PPI) involves a process of introspection and self-reflection, allowing individuals to assess their past experiences, emotions, and thoughts without hindering their present journey. This practice enables individuals to gain insight into themselves, their beliefs, values, motivations, strengths, weaknesses, and goals. Through self-examination, individuals can explore their inner world, identify patterns, and evaluate areas for improvement or growth. Ultimately, self-examination fosters greater self-awareness, personal growth, and positive change (Ackerman, 2020). These experiences serve as catalysts for practitioners to become the best versions of themselves in the present. Participant 5 reflected on their experience: "I used PP in terms of looking back at what happened in my past. It was no longer depressing; instead, I appreciated it. It was painful, but I feel grateful for that part. I'm thankful it happened. Even though it wasn't good back then, it turned out to be beautiful and positive," Participant 6 added. "Because a lot of things happen in life, finding meaning is one principle of PP. Every time I look back, I'm not sad about that time. But now, it feels sad because I came to a point where there was so much depression that I didn't feel anything anymore. That has been the greatest struggle. So whenever I look at the PP, I understand that those events had to happen, or I would not be in my current position." Participant 8's perspective is to let go of having things together. "What will help me focus on the other person rather than be caught up in whatever is happening in my life? At the same time, it also allows me to not be perfect, right? It takes off the pressure to be perfect or to have everything." (2) Self-compassion: Practitioners have embraced self-compassion, enabling them to be kind, non-judgmental, and caring towards themselves and others, especially their clients. Despite their professional roles as clinicians, practitioners recognize their shared humanity and the need for self-compassion when faced with adversities. They consistently apply PPI tools to equip themselves for unexpected circumstances. As participant 6 stated how self-compassion helped him during shortcomings; "Self-compassion is the ability to direct your feelings of empathy and care toward yourself, to see your own shortcomings, flaws, imperfections, and suffering without judgment, and to care for yourself despite these things. I have made so many mistakes." She added, "I was able to understand the feelings of regret. I was able to understand how my clients, being able to find meaning in their experiences, find it more bearable in the present time. Because of the principles of PP, it gives me a foundation." Participants 8 added of being kind to self when not feeling well and allowing herself to be vulnerable. In line with this, research conducted by self-compassion expert Kristin Neff argues that individuals characterized by higher levels of self-compassion often demonstrate elevated levels of happiness, life satisfaction, and motivation. They tend to foster healthier relationships and experience improved physical well-being, while also reporting reduced levels of anxiety and depression. Additionally, self-compassionate individuals exhibit heightened resilience, enabling them to effectively navigate challenging life circumstances (Neff & Germer, 2019). These findings are observed to contribute to the personal

growth of practitioners (participants). (3). Self-improvement: Through Positive Psychology Interventions (PPIs) and their own life trials, practitioners have acknowledged the importance of developing both soft and hard skills in all areas of life, including careers and relationships. They have cultivated resilience, resourcefulness, people-oriented skills, effective decision-making abilities, practicality, confidence, and self-motivation. These developments contribute to their personal flourishing and thriving. Participant 6 claimed to have improved resourcefulness, assertiveness, and decision-making skills, stating, "I was able to be very resourceful, research-oriented, and practical. I know when to decide whether a decision fulfills me or not. I became assertive, knowing whether a person is helpful for my mental and physical health. It's the little skills, the necessary skills, interpersonal skills, and life skills. Being street-smart—those things were given meaning because of the concept of Positive Psychology." Participant 7 reported an improvement in confidence, stating, "When I was applying PPIs, I gained confidence in myself." and lastly, Participant 8 recognized that life is not about luck but rather about taking action toward what we want. Overall, the personal growth experienced by practitioners through PPI not only enhances their own lives but also positively influences their ability to support and guide their clients. By embodying the principles and practices of PPI, practitioners can create an environment conducive to flourishing and promote the well-being of both themselves and their clients (D'raven, & Pasha-Zaidi, 2014).

Perceived Effectiveness

Gratitude

The observation of gratitude behaviors among clients by participants 4 and 6 serves as compelling evidence of the efficacy of gratitude exercises within the therapeutic setting. This observation implies that such interventions not only foster personal growth and well-being among clients but also strengthen the therapeutic bond between clients and their clinicians. When clients express gratitude towards their clinicians, it signifies a deep sense of trust, appreciation, and recognition for the support and guidance received throughout their therapeutic journey. One notable finding from the study, as reported by participant 6, highlights the presence of gratitude behaviors exhibited by clients, which can be seen as an indicator of successful therapy sessions. These expressions of gratitude take various forms, including clients sending food or heartfelt text messages with expressions of "thank you's". Participant 6 remarked, "Most of my clients message me because they feel happy with their progress and success in addressing their life challenges. I believe this demonstrates the effectiveness of positive psychology interventions. They express sincere gratitude, sometimes even bringing food as a token of appreciation, which reinforces my belief in the efficacy of these interventions." In contrast, participant 4 assesses the success of sessions based on self-reports provided by clients. He noted, "I gauge success through self-reports. Clients express gratitude for the insights gained and for the positive psychology techniques, such as self-compassion, which they hadn't previously considered. Their newfound realization of these aspects underscores the effectiveness of the interventions." Both participants' (4 and 6) perspectives underscore the importance of gratitude in the therapeutic process and highlight how its expression can serve as a barometer for the effectiveness of interventions. This observation aligns with the application of gratitude exercises or other activities, which are among the Positive Psychology Interventions (PPI) employed in therapy sessions. The incorporation of these tools enables clients to generalize gratitude practices beyond the therapy setting to their interactions with their respective clinicians (Oppland, 2017).

Holistic Healing

Most of the participants of the study have recognized the advantages of integrating positive psychology interventions (PPI) as an integral component of their therapeutic sessions (Duckworth et al., 2005). By incorporating adapted and applied positive psychology tools alongside traditional interventions, substantial positive outcomes have been observed among clients across multiple dimensions, encompassing improvements in physical health, emotional well-being, and psychological growth (Benneth, 2018).

In terms of physical health, participants 5, 6, and 7 observed a significant improvement in their clients' overall well-being. Participant 5 noted a noticeable transformation in their clients' physical appearance as they regained their desired physique. Moreover, participant 7 observed a reduction in fidgeting behaviors among clients, indicating an increased sense of calmness and improved self-regulation. Narratives from participants further support these observations. Participants 5 and 6 emphasized the physical changes, with one stating, "Physically, of course, they get back into shape, become more comfortable with their aura, more cheerful maybe, sleep well, eat well. That's what matters." Participant 6 also mentioned monitoring physical symptoms, particularly panic attacks, and noticed a reduction, indicating improvement in clients' physical well-being. Participant 7 observed a non-verbal cue of increased glow on clients' faces, signifying positive transformation in physical well-being. Positive health extends beyond the mere absence of disease. It includes longevity, fewer ailments, improved recovery, faster wound healing, increased physiological reserves, and the management of chronic yet non-debilitating conditions. Research indicates that positive health assets reliably predict favorable health outcomes across various measures. Positive psychological factors linked to better health include positive emotions, life satisfaction, optimism, forgiveness, self-regulation, vitality, life meaning, altruism, social connections, and spirituality (Park et al., 2016).

In addition to physical improvements, participants' 5, 6 and 7 clients' demonstrated notable advancements in emotional regulation and awareness. They exhibited proficiency in recognizing and effectively managing their emotions, leading to a state of happiness reflected in their outward demeanor. Participants shared their observations in this area as well. Participant 5 noted, "Emotionally, they can now control or manage their emotions. They are more likely to regulate their feelings; if they still feel sadness, fear, or anger, it's manageable, unlike before." Participant 7 added the same observations: "Regarding their emotions, they already know how to handle them. For example, when they are angry, they already know how to manage it." Participant 6 reported observing emotional growth in

clients when they exhibit minimal sadness while engaging in their work as reported.

Lastly, 3 of the participants agreed and acknowledged that Positive Psychology Interventions can significantly complement the sessions. They also agree that these tools can enhance clients' psychological well-being. These are the indicators of psychological growth among clients, as reported by participants 3, 5, and 7: Participant 3 observed increased attentiveness and reduced impulsivity in their clients. They noted, "We have observed that patients are more attentive to our discussions, and they themselves claim to be less impulsive. This reduction in impulsive or repetitive behaviors that lead nowhere or have no purpose has become apparent." Participant 5 noted that their clients exhibit a greater sense of control over their lives. Lastly, participant 7 observed a maturation in their clients' mindset, as evidenced by the development of life direction and the establishment of plans for self-improvement.

Positive psychology interventions have a significant impact on overall well-being across various dimensions, including physical, emotional, psychological, and spiritual aspects. Research indicates that a variety of positive psychology intervention (PPI) activities enhance subjective well-being (Heintzelman, Kushlev, & Diener, 2023). These benefits are aligned with the principles of positive psychology interventions, illustrating a holistic approach to promoting individuals' overall well-being (Bennet, 2018). Integrating these tools into holistic healing practices facilitates comprehensive growth and transformation among clients, addressing their physical, emotional, and psychological needs simultaneously (Barron, 2023).

Limitations

One significant limitation of positive psychology interventions (PPIs) in clinical practice pertains to their effectiveness in severe mental health conditions based on the participants' observations. In instances where clients are experiencing severe mental illnesses, PPIs alone may not be sufficient, and medication may be required as part of an effective treatment approach. Certain mental disorders, such as panic disorders, generalized anxiety disorders with biological causes, schizophrenia, narcissistic personality disorder, and post-traumatic spectrum disorder (PTSD) with late onset, are considered to be among the most severe forms of mental illness. Congruent with the participants observation, according to MantraCare.org, the prevailing discourse in positive psychology tends to prioritize individual experiences over broader societal dynamics, thereby overlooking crucial societal implications. Furthermore, the lack of a standardized scientific methodology for evaluating the impacts of positive psychology interventions poses a significant challenge. This gap hinders the accumulation of robust empirical evidence necessary for establishing the efficacy of such interventions. Moreover, the field's emphasis on enhancing well-being may inadvertently overshadow the pressing need for addressing severe mental health issues, potentially leaving individuals with significant psychological distress without adequate support (Reinfeld, n.d.).

These are the experiences of participants with positive psychology interventions limitations in their sessions. It was concluded that the use of these interventions might not be helpful, particularly when medications are deemed necessary. Participant 3 shared their perspective, stating, "It's not ideal for people with anxiety disorders such as generalized anxiety disorder or panic disorder. All interventions have their weaknesses, and they may not achieve the highest efficacy for certain groups of people. However, I'm not saying it's ineffective for anxiety and panic disorder; it just takes time for the chemical balance in their bodies to settle, and for the patient to empower themselves to stay calm. It can become intrusive, with flashbacks or images that cause more tension. That's been my experience with them."

Participants 5 and 8 emphasized that positive psychology interventions would not be effective for conditions such as schizophrenia, bipolar disorder, narcissism, and histrionic personality disorder. They noted: "It's definitely not schizophrenia, nor bipolar disorder. Additionally, I feel it won't be effective for narcissistic and histrionic personality disorders," (P5) and Participant 8 added, "Let's consider a personality disorder, such as Narcissism. In Positive Psychology, if you focus on 'what's great about you?' it might actually exacerbate the narcissism of the person. If narcissism interferes with the relationship, rather than helping them and the relationship, it doesn't ground the person in reality." and finally, Participant 6, who noted that in cases of PTSD with late onset, the condition can worsen when using positive psychology interventions alone.

Contrary to participants' observations, the systematic review and meta-analysis of Pina et al. (2020), explored the efficacy of Positive Psychology Interventions (PPIs) in enhancing well-being and alleviating symptoms among individuals diagnosed with schizophrenia spectrum disorders. The study investigates nine clinical trials employing various PPI protocols, such as Loving-Kindness Meditation (LKM) and mindfulness, and highlights the increasing interest in positive psychology within psychiatric research. While PPIs demonstrate potential in improving well-being outcomes and reducing negative symptoms, the review emphasizes the need for further research to establish standardized protocols and enhance comparability across studies.

To address concerns raised by participants regarding the effectiveness of Positive Psychology Interventions (PPIs) for personality disorders, it's important to recognize a significant research gap in the study of cluster A personality disorders. These disorders, characterized by traits such as aloofness and peculiarity, present diagnostic challenges, as noted by therapists (O'Keefe Osborn, C., 2018). Similarly, cluster C personality disorders, characterized by traits of avoidance and anxiety, also lack sufficient attention in research (WebMD Editorial Contributors, 2024). Most research and meta-analyses on personality disorders predominantly focus on borderline personality disorder (BPD) (National Collaborating Centre for Mental Health (UK), 2009). In these studies, dialectical behavior therapy (DBT) and psychodynamic therapy emerge as the most common treatments for BPD, while positive psychology interventions are notably absent. Furthermore, the effectiveness of therapeutic interventions for BPD appears varied, with mixed

outcomes reported (Cristea et al., 2017).

The second limitation of Positive Psychology Interventions (PPIs) is their effectiveness when used in isolation, without integrating them with traditional psychological approaches, as emphasized by participants 6 and 8. They highlighted the shortcomings of relying solely on PPIs as a treatment approach, particularly for severe disorders. Participant 6 noted, "I don't think it can stand alone; if used alone, it's a very weak therapeutic style," a sentiment supported by participant 8, who stated, "I think with clinical cases, they can't stand on their own because even Martin Seligman has a lot to do with CBT. He has his ABCD Model, which is like the whole CBT part of things; that's also part of the PPI." Conversely, a study reviewing eighteen trials on standalone mindfulness interventions for anxiety and depression yielded contradictory results. Blanck et al. (2018) concluded that mindfulness exercises showed moderate effectiveness in symptom reduction, suggesting its potential as a standalone intervention worthy of further exploration in clinical settings. However, a study by Marrero and colleagues (2016) opposes standalone PPI interventions, arguing that positive psychology is often integrated with Cognitive Behavioral Therapy (CBT), which aids in addressing negative beliefs. The integration of CBT strategies within Positive Psychology Interventions holds great potential for individuals to analyze their thought processes, an essential aspect of reorienting their worldview toward a more positive outlook. This integration facilitates the transformation of maladaptive thoughts and behaviors into more constructive patterns, thus promoting overall well-being. Techniques such as mental imagery can help individuals visualize positive outcomes and cultivate an optimistic mindset. Similarly, cognitive restructuring techniques, such as challenging negative beliefs and replacing them with positive and realistic ones, allow individuals to reframe their thinking patterns and foster a more positive cognitive framework. Recent research suggests that the combination of CBT and PPI approaches can enhance the efficacy of interventions.

Another important aspect of the contextual limitations within a clinical setting pertains to the impact of the participants' client's environment on the effectiveness of positive psychology interventions (PPIs).

Participants 4, 5 and 6 have recognized that the ongoing challenges and circumstances that their clients face in their environment or living conditions can hinder their progress and ability to overcome traumatic experiences. Participant 4 highlighted the difficulties encountered when working with clients who are not fully present in their current environment, particularly in cases of dissociation where the environment serves as triggers for past traumatic experiences. Participant 5 emphasized the significance of a supportive environment, stating, "And at the same time, your environment should also be supportive. If the environment isn't conducive during the sessions, that's the first issue. You must separate the client from the abusive or toxic environment. It seems like we're just putting a band-aid on the wounds," Participant 6 further added, "If there is psychological abuse, I don't think it's too helpful, such as in cases of family sexual assault. I believe you're not effective when they're still in a stressful environment because you can't talk about the future being bright if they are constantly reminded that the problem is there." The practitioners emphasized that not having a healthy environment while undergoing a session impacted the clients' progress in therapy, as having a healthy living condition is pivotal to the clients' fast recovery (Barker, 2022). Additionally, according to Linberg (2021), various stress-inducing factors, including indirect communication, conflicts, or unreliable individuals within the client's environment, can impede the effectiveness of positive psychology interventions. While the aim of these interventions is to promote well-being and resilience, the presence of ongoing environmental stressors, such as dysfunctional relationships, unsupportive social networks, or adverse living conditions, can hinder the desired outcomes of the interventions. Consequently, it becomes crucial to address these environmental factors in order to enhance the success of the intervention (Linberg, 2021). Therefore, in clinical practice, therapists must consider and address the client's environmental context, ensuring that a supportive and conducive environment is established to maximize the effectiveness of positive psychology interventions.

Lastly, another important factor that needs to be addressed is the resistance exhibited by the participants' clients towards accepting positive psychology interventions (PPIs) as part of their therapeutic treatment during sessions. Clients' resistance in therapeutic sessions can be influenced by various factors. As observed, participant 3 noted the lack of insight and understanding of the therapy process could be a possible reason for resistance. In the case of participants 4, 5, and 7, their observations during sessions indicated that clients may not believe in the effectiveness of the interventions or may hold beliefs that they do not deserve them. These observations suggest the presence of underlying issues that warrant further exploration. Participant 4 mentioned, "Maybe they don't believe in the quality, they feel they don't deserve it, maybe a lot of layers are still needed for these qualities to flourish and thrive." Participant 5 emphasized that through conversations or interviews, it becomes evident that some clients are not open to accepting certain interventions. Participant 7 added, "At first, there are others who are shy and do not believe it (about the interventions), even though I explained it to them at the start." In accordance with Sutton (2021), it is crucial for practitioners to exercise caution when attributing a client's behaviors as 'resistant,' as such behaviors may stem from a lack of knowledge or therapeutic skills. However, aside from the aforementioned reasons for resistance, there are other factors contributing to clients' resistance. Possible explanations could include clients perceiving inadequacies in the practitioners' knowledge and proficiency in utilizing and explaining therapeutic tools (Clay, 2017). Additionally, clients themselves may harbor doubts, exhibit resistance, or be in denial, affecting interventions' efficacy. Lastly, it is plausible that prescribed interventions (PPIs) are unsuitable for the client's condition or diagnosis, or the client may choose not to participate in therapy sessions for personal reasons, thus further impacting efficacy (Sutton, 2021).

In conclusion, while Positive Psychology Interventions offer numerous benefits in clinical practice, it is important to recognize their limitations (Sutton, 2021). Severe mental health conditions (Pina et al., 2021; Feliu-Soler et al., 2016), the need for integration with

other therapeutic approaches (Chaves, Lopez-Gomez, Hervas, & Vazquez, 2017), the influence of the client's environment (Linberg, 2021), and the potential overemphasis on positivity are factors that can hinder the effectiveness of these interventions (Lomas, Hefferon, & Ivtzan, 2015). Addressing these limitations and considering individual circumstances can help therapists tailor their approach and provide more comprehensive and effective treatment for their clients.

Conclusion

To address the two objectives of the study, (1). the experiences of a Clinical Psychologist in practicing Positive Psychology Interventions (PPIs) can be summarized as follows:

The practitioner's experiences in utilizing PPIs were categorized into several main themes, namely: Integrated Practices, Adapted Method, Applied Interventions, and Personal Growth. These themes demonstrate how practitioners incorporate PPIs into their work by combining them with traditional therapeutic interventions. This blended approach has yielded significantly positive outcomes compared to using standalone interventions (Chaves, Lopez-Gomez, Hervas, & Vazquez (2017). Additionally, practitioners have modified certain strategies from PPIs to align them with their therapeutic plans (Hendriks et al., 2019). Furthermore, practitioners recognize that PPIs can be applied across various settings due to their non-invasive nature and user-friendly approach (Parks, 2015). Finally, it is worth noting that incorporating PPIs into their practice has had a profound impact on practitioners' lives, not only in their work with clients but also in their personal and career development(D'raven, & Pasha-Zaidi, 2014).

(2). The participants' descriptions of the perceived effectiveness of using positive psychology interventions in their clinical practice can be examined within the context of three themes: Gratitude, holistic healing, and limitations. In the context of the gratitude theme, practitioners noted the profound significance of their clients' expressions of gratitude in their healing journey and holds importance to the therapy's success (Oppland, 2017). Participants highlighted the effectiveness of positive psychology interventions in facilitating holistic healing. They emphasized the importance of addressing not only the symptoms but also the underlying strengths and positive aspects of individuals. By integrating positive psychology interventions into their therapeutic approach, participants witnessed clients experiencing a more comprehensive and balanced healing process (Chaves, Lopez-Gomez, Hervas, & Vazquez, 2017). These interventions helped clients develop resilience, tap into their inner strengths, and foster a positive mindset, which positively influenced their overall well-being (Niemiec, 2023). And lastly limitations, while participants acknowledged the benefits of positive psychology interventions, they also recognized certain limitations. They discussed the need for a nuanced approach and the importance of considering individual differences when implementing these interventions. Some participants observed that certain clients were initially resistant or skeptical towards positive psychology interventions, requiring a tailored and gradual introduction. Additionally, participants acknowledged that positive psychology interventions may not be suitable for everyone or every presenting issue, and they emphasized the need to integrate them within a broader therapeutic framework. It is important to note that while positive psychology interventions have demonstrated promising results, their effectiveness may vary depending on individual characteristics, contextual factors, and the specific intervention employed (Sutton, 2021). Additionally, it is crucial to consider a holistic approach to mental health and well-being, incorporating both positive psychology interventions and traditional evidence-based practices, for comprehensive and personalized care.

As part of the recommendations for future research and implementation, it is advised that researchers further establish the years of practice of Filipino psychologists who utilize Positive Psychology Interventions (PPIs) within their clinical practices. This exploration should be considered as part of the demographic profile analysis, providing insights into the practitioners' experience and expertise. Additionally, to enhance the robustness of the research findings, it is recommended to increase the number of participants in future studies by adding 3 or 4 more participants. This will allow for more comprehensive and representative data, with a minimum of five years of utilizing positive psychology interventions in their respective sessions, thereby contributing to a better understanding of the effectiveness and impact of PPIs in the clinical context. Moreover, while exploring cultural appropriateness is a good recommendation, it is suggested that future researchers investigate within the Filipino context, such as collectivism and family values. By focusing on these specific cultural dimensions, researchers can gain deeper insights into how PPIs can be tailored to align with the values, beliefs, and cultural norms of the Filipino population, thereby enhancing their effectiveness and applicability in clinical settings.

Lastly, to expand the body of knowledge in the clinical realm, it is highly recommended to conduct further research in the Philippine context. This research should specifically focus on the cultural appropriateness of PPIs, ensuring that these interventions are suitable and aligned with the values, beliefs, and cultural norms of the Filipino population. By conducting research in the local context, the findings can be more applicable and beneficial for practitioners and individuals seeking psychological support in the Philippines.

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Affiliations and Corresponding Information

Hannah Mae B. Gabuyo

Polytechnic University of the Philippines – Philippines

Dr. Pricila B. Marzan

Polytechnic University of the Philippines – Philippines